

1 **MgO/NiAl₂O₄ AS A NEW FORMULATION OF REFORMING**
2 **CATALYSTS. TUNING THE SURFACE PROPERTIES FOR THE**
3 **ENHANCED PARTIAL OXIDATION OF METHANE**

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22 **Abstract**

23 Magnesia modified nickel aluminate spinel catalysts were synthesised and characterised
24 by BET, TEM, XRD, H₂-TPR, XPS, CO₂-TPD and TGA-MS techniques. The addition
25 of this promoter induced significant changes in the textural, structural and chemical
26 properties of the resulting spinel derived catalysts. Thus, it enhanced the resistance of
27 the deposited Ni particles against sintering, whereas, upon increasing MgO loading, it
28 drastically modified the density and the strength of the surface basic sites. In fact, an
29 apparent weakening of the surface basic sites with the abundance of highly dispersed
30 Mg species was interestingly observed.

31 The changes provoked by MgO addition deeply influenced the catalytic performance of
32 the prepared samples in the partial oxidation of methane reaction at 700 °C. In this
33 sense, it was found a good correlation between the measured density of the strong basic
34 sites on the different samples, including the bare NiAl₂O₄, and their catalytic activity.
35 Hence, the MgO(5 wt.)/NiAl₂O₄ sample, with a magnesium loading close to the
36 theoretical monolayer and the lowest strong basic density sites, exhibited the best
37 catalytic performance under both stoichiometric (O/C = 1) and non-stoichiometric
38 (O/C = 0.75) conditions during a relatively prolonged time on stream.

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41 *Keywords: Nickel aluminate, magnesium oxide, surface basicity, partial oxidation of*
42 *methane*

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46 1. Introduction

47 The application of energy technology based on hydrogen as energy vector is a
48 promising alternative, to traditional fossil fuels combustions, which could facilitate the
49 transition to a sustainable development of clean energy systems [1-3]. Nowadays,
50 hydrogen is mostly produced via steam reforming of methane (SRM, Ec. (1)).
51 Nevertheless, this process is relatively expensive due to its high endothermicity [4, 5].
52 For this reason the partial oxidation of methane (POM, Ec. (2)) is often viewed as a
53 more advantageous strategy since the process needs a lower energy input due to its mild
54 exothermicity, which reduces operation costs. Thus, the technology does not need an
55 external fired heater which makes it simpler and more practical for small reactors used
56 in mobile applications [6-9]. Furthermore, the POM is a good option when the posterior
57 use of the syngas stream requires a suitable H₂/CO ratio. Nevertheless, there are many
58 parallel reactions that could occur during the POM process, such as water gas shift
59 reaction (WGS, Ec. (3)) and/or methane total oxidation (Ec. (4)), which produce
60 significant amounts of carbon dioxide in the product gas [10-12].

65 It is known that noble metals, such as Rh and Pt, exhibit a good reforming activity and
66 high resistance against carbon formation. However, this high cost limits their utilisation.
67 As a result, research is extensively focused on other promising substitutes based on
68 active transition metals [11, 13-15]. Among the non-noble metals, Ni-based catalysts
69 have similar activity compared to those based on noble metals [9, 13, 16, 17].
70 Nevertheless, they are very sensitive to the structural changes that can affect their active

71 species under the severe conditions of the preparation (reduction at high temperatures)
72 and during the reforming catalytic process. According to many authors these changes
73 may provoke decay in their activity and stability [16-22]. In this sense, many efforts
74 have been devoted to develop active and stable catalysts (minimizing sintering and
75 coking) by optimising the preparation route to achieve high nickel dispersion. In this
76 sense, the literature proposes some strategies based on the preparation of spinel
77 (NiM_2O_4) [18, 19] or perovskite (MNiO_3) [20-22] phases as catalyst precursors, where
78 nickel is stabilised in a well-defined structure. For instance, in our previous studies we
79 demonstrated that the NiAl_2O_4 spinel materials, reduced at high temperature (850 °C),
80 led to a formation of metallic nickel supported on alumina surface with high dispersion
81 and relatively small crystallite size [13, 23]. These synthesised catalysts proved high
82 activity, selectivity and stability in various methane reforming reactions, compared to
83 those prepared by conventional routes.

84 Also, within the objective to improve activity and stability of Ni catalysts, by reducing
85 the Ni crystallites sizes and their stabilisation against sintering, the effect of the addition
86 of some alkali and alkaline earth metals used as chemical promoters has been
87 extensively investigated [8, 24-26]. For instance, Sousa et al. [27] studied the
88 relationship between structure and deactivation in the dry reforming of methane over
89 Ni/alumina doped with CeO_2 , MgO , ZrO_2 and La_2O_3 catalysts. Their results showed that
90 the catalyst promoted with MgO exhibited the highest performance amongst all the
91 investigated materials. This behaviour was explained by a synergetic effect between
92 nickel species and $\text{MgAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4$ structures which enhanced the resistance to
93 structural transformations and inhibited carbon formation. By contrast, Kirillov et al. [9]
94 observed some structural changes on Ni/ MgO /alumina catalysts used in partial
95 oxidation of methane for 100 h, but this was not at the expense of their activity. Besides

96 its promotional effect on the structural properties of Ni catalysts many investigations
97 highlighted the suitable surface basicity provided by MgO promoter which greatly
98 influences the adsorption-desorption of reaction intermediates and thus the catalytic
99 reforming performance [28].

100 The major objective of this work is the analysis of textural, chemical and structural
101 properties and catalytic behaviour of a set of nickel aluminate samples with varying the
102 amount of MgO promoter. The choice of the magnesia loading in the 2.5-10 wt.% range
103 has been made in accordance with the BET surface area of the prepared catalysts to
104 obtain surface Mg densities ranging from sub-monolayer to over-monolayer values. It
105 should be noted that, to our knowledge, the modification of NiAl₂O₄ spinel materials
106 with MgO, their characterisation and their catalytic performance in the POM reaction
107 have not been yet investigated. Special attention has been devoted to the influence of
108 MgO loading on the physico-chemical and catalytic properties of the reduced
109 MgO/NiAl₂O₄ samples.

110

111 **2. Experimental**

112 *2.1. Catalysts preparation*

113 Bulk NiAl₂O₄ (MgO(0)-NiAl sample) was synthesised from a mixture of two aqueous
114 solutions Ni(CH₃-COO)₂·4H₂O and Al(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, with the desired 1:2 Ni/Al molar
115 ratio. The final pH of the aqueous solution was adjusted at 8 by adding aqueous
116 ammonia (0.6 M). The precipitate was subsequently aged for 30 minutes before being
117 filtered and washed with hot deionised water. Afterwards the recovered solid was dried
118 at 110 °C overnight and then calcined at 850 °C in static air for 4 h at a heating rate of
119 10 °C min⁻¹ [23].

120 The incorporation of magnesium oxide on the nickel aluminate (3 g) was carried out by
121 wet impregnation with an aqueous solution of $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The samples were dried
122 at 110 °C overnight and then calcined at 850 °C in static air for 2 h using a heating rate
123 of 10 °C min^{-1} . The catalysts were labelled MgO(2.5)-NiAl, MgO(5)-NiAl, MgO(7)-
124 NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl, which corresponded to MgO loadings of 2.5, 5, 7 and
125 10 wt.%, respectively. NiO and MgO pure oxides were prepared by simple calcination
126 at 850 °C in air of nickel acetate and magnesium nitrate, respectively. Referring to the
127 MgAl_2O_4 sample was obtained commercially from Sigma-Aldrich.

128 2.2. Catalyst characterisation

129 The catalysts were characterised by N_2 physisorption at -196 °C, wavelength dispersive
130 X-ray fluorescence (WDXRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), temperature programmed
131 reduction with hydrogen (H_2 -TPR), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS),
132 transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and temperature programmed desorption of
133 CO_2 (CO_2 -TPD). The experimental details of each analytical technique were described
134 elsewhere [13, 23].

135 Additionally, the surface basicity of the reduced samples was characterised by
136 temperature programmed desorption of CO_2 techniques (CO_2 -TPD). These studies were
137 carried out on an experimental setup coupled to a MKS Cirrus LM99 mass
138 spectrometer. Prior to running the TPD experiments, the oxide samples (200 mg) were
139 submitted to a pre-treatment routine consisting of a reduction step at 850 °C (2 h) in a
140 flow 5% H_2 /Ar, cooling to 40 °C in a flow of He, treatment in a flow of CO_2 /He for 1 h
141 at 40 °C, and finally 1 h under flowing He, also at 40 °C. The thermo desorption of CO_2
142 step was carried out under He flow rate of 50 $\text{cm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$ and a heating ramp of
143 10 °C min^{-1} (up to 900 °C).

144 The spent samples were characterised by S_{BET} measurements, XRD, TEM and
145 thermogravimetry coupled to mass spectrometry (TGA-MS).

146 2.3. Catalytic tests

147 Catalytic tests were performed in a bench-scale fixed-bed reactor (Microactivity
148 modular laboratory system provided by PID Eng&Tech S.L) operated at atmospheric
149 pressure and fully monitored by computer. The reactor was made of stainless steel with
150 an internal diameter of 9 mm and a height of 305 mm, in which the temperature was
151 controlled by a thermocouple placed in the catalyst bed. Typically 0.125 g of catalyst in
152 powdered form (0.3-0.5 mm) was loaded. The catalysts bed was diluted with inert
153 quartz 1:1 (1-1.25 mm). Different experiments were carried out to evaluate the catalytic
154 activity and stability of the samples. Firstly, a feed gas mixture containing 10%CH₄,
155 5%O₂ (O/C = 1) and balanced with N₂ was used. Hence, a volume hourly space velocity
156 at 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ was maintained using Bronkhorst mass flow controllers.
157 Before the reaction, the catalyst was reduced *in situ* under 5%H₂/N₂ at 850 °C for 2 h.
158 The experiments were carried out at constant temperature (700 °C) for about 20 h.
159 The catalysts were also intentionally run under more severe conditions to allow
160 meaningful reactivity and stability comparison. Thus, maintaining the same time on
161 stream (20 h) and operation temperature (700 °C), the volume hourly space velocity at
162 60000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ (15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂) was increased while the O/C mole
163 ratio was lowered down to 0.75. Additional experiments were conducted over a more
164 prolonged time on line (75 h).

165 On basis of the dry molar flow at the inlet and outlet of the reactor, conversion and
166 product yields were calculated, according to the following equations:

$$167 \quad X(\text{CH}_4), \% = \frac{F_{\text{out}}(\text{CO}) + F_{\text{out}}(\text{CO}_2)}{F_{\text{in}}(\text{CH}_4)} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

168
$$Y(H_2) = \frac{F_{out}(H_2)}{2 \cdot F_{in}(CH_4)} \quad (6)$$

169
$$Y(CO) = \frac{F_{out}(CO)}{F_{in}(CH_4)} \quad (7)$$

170
$$Y(CO_2) = \frac{F_{out}(CO_2)}{F_{in}(CH_4)} \quad (8)$$

171

172 **3. Results and discussion**

173 *3.1. Characterisation of the fresh samples*

174 *3.1.1. N₂-physorption (BET measurements)*

175 The textural properties of the calcined and reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts were
176 examined by nitrogen adsorption-desorption measurements. All the samples exhibited
177 IV-type isotherms, indicating the existence of well-developed mesopores, with
178 significantly reduced hysteresis loops (not shown). The corresponding specific surface
179 area values are reported in Table 1. The magnesia unmodified catalyst (MgO(0)-NiAl)
180 presented a specific surface area of 75 m² g⁻¹. Upon addition of MgO the surface area
181 significantly decreased. Hence, for MgO-rich samples it was 61 m² g⁻¹ for
182 MgO(7)-NiAl and 59 m² g⁻¹ for MgO(10)-NiAl.

183 The reduction of the MgO(0)-NiAl catalyst provoked a significant drop (about 10%) in
184 its specific surface area, from 75 to 67 m² g⁻¹. However, this loss of surface area
185 associated with the phase transformation from NiAl₂O₄ to Ni/Al₂O₃ was less evident in
186 the presence of increased amounts of Mg. Thus, this resistance against the decrease of
187 surface area was notably enhanced with MgO loading. For instance, the reduction of the
188 sample with the highest MgO loading, MgO(10)-NiAl, did not affect its specific surface
189 area (59 m² g⁻¹).

190 Figure 1 shows the pore size distributions of the reduced samples. The shape of the
191 traces of the samples with a low MgO loading ($\leq 5\%$) looked similar. Their distribution
192 were, thus, characterised by a main peak centred at approximately 18 nm and a shoulder
193 at 14 nm. However, for higher MgO loadings ($\geq 7\%$) the pore sizes had a unimodal
194 distribution located at 18 nm, thereby revealing the absence of narrower pores peak
195 (at 14 nm). Since the surface density of Mg atoms in the MgO(5)-NiAl sample was
196 11.8 at. nm^{-2} , very close to the theoretical surface monolayer, 12.4 at. nm^{-2} , we might
197 reasonably conclude that most of narrow pores of MgO-rich samples were completely
198 filled by the over-monolayer Mg species.

199 Table 1/Figure 1

200 3.1.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

201 The MgO(x)-NiAl samples were also characterised by means of X-ray powder
202 diffraction in order to investigate the effect of the MgO addition on their structural
203 properties. Figure 2 compares the XRD patterns for all the prepared MgO(x)-NiAl in
204 their calcined (850 °C) and reduced (850 °C) states (Figure 2 (a) and Figure 2 (b),
205 respectively). The crystalline phases were identified using the JCPDS files. Expectedly
206 the calcined MgO(0)-NiAl sample displayed a set of diffraction peaks centred at
207 $2\theta = 19.3^\circ, 31.5^\circ, 37.2^\circ, 45.2^\circ, 59.9^\circ$ and 65.7° , assignable to the nickel aluminate phase
208 (JCPDS 78-1601) [29]. Furthermore, the MgO(0)-NiAl diffractogram showed additional
209 peaks associated with NiO structure, at 43.6° and 62.9° (JCPDS 89-7131). It should be
210 noted that the XRD patterns of the calcined MgO catalysts showed a significant
211 evolution of the NiO diffraction peaks which shifted to lower angles. This effect was
212 more pronounced on the MgO-rich samples. For instance, 2θ angle shifted from 43.6°
213 for MgO(0)-NiAl sample to 43.5° and 43.4° for MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl,
214 respectively. These observations suggested the diffusion of Mg^{2+} cations in NiO crystal

215 lattice to form MgO-NiO solid solution [26]. Moreover, the slight shift might be
216 explained by the identical structures of NiO and MgO phases and their very close lattice
217 parameters.

218 Figure 2 (b) includes the diffractograms of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts after reduction at
219 850 °C. As expected, the MgO(0)-NiAl pattern showed a transformation of nickel
220 aluminate and NiO structures into gamma alumina (JCPDS 79-1558) and metallic
221 nickel (JCPDS 89-7128) phases. Apparently, no diffraction peaks associated with NiO
222 or MgO were visible in the patterns of MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts. However, because of its
223 high formation heat, above 420 kJ mol⁻¹, the reduction of magnesium oxide under the
224 used reduction conditions (850 °C for 2 h) was ruled out. Then, the structural changes of
225 Mg species provoked by the reduction process were followed by assessing the
226 diffraction lines attributed to gamma alumina which seemed to shift to lower angles
227 with MgO. Figure 3 shows a correlation between the lattice parameter corresponding to
228 gamma alumina structure and the Mg/Al molar ratios determined by WDXRF, for all
229 the reduced samples and for pure MgAl₂O₄ used as reference. The results clearly
230 indicated a shift of the lattice parameter (a) towards higher values with MgO loading,
231 thereby suggesting a progressive formation of MgAl₂O₄. In their study on NiSn/MgO-
232 Al₂O₃ materials Penkova et al. [30] attributed this shift to the formation of magnesium
233 aluminate phase. In this sense Jacob et al. [31] also reported that the formation of
234 MgAl₂O₄ from MgO and Al₂O₃ could start at around 800 °C.

235 The average size of Ni particles calculated by Scherrer equation was found to be around
236 11 nm on the MgO(0)-NiAl catalyst while somewhat smaller particles with an average
237 size of about 9-9.5 nm were detected for the magnesia modified catalysts (Table 2). We
238 might conclude that the deposition of MgO enhanced the resistance against metallic
239 nickel sintering.

240

241 *3.1.3. Temperature programmed reduction (H₂-TPR)*

242 The H₂-TPR experiments were performed in order to identify the various Ni reducible
243 species and the influence of MgO on the reducibility of the calcined MgO(x)-NiAl
244 samples (Figure 4). It should be noted that no reduction peaks were detected on the
245 H₂-TPR profiles of MgAl₂O₄ and MgO samples used as reference (not displayed). The
246 H₂-TPR curve of MgO(0)-NiAl sample exhibited a typical profile of non-stoichiometric
247 nickel aluminate materials. This exhibited three reduction peaks centred at 490, 720 and
248 805 °C. The former, α -type NiO, was attributed to the reduction of NiO species which
249 had strong interaction with the spinel phase. The two high-temperature reduction peaks
250 at 720 and 805 °C were associated with the reduction of the Ni²⁺ species incorporated in
251 an inverse nickel aluminate structure. In our previous study we proved that, in an
252 inverse spinel structure, the Ni²⁺ ions located in octahedral sites (β -type NiO) were
253 more prone to be reduced compared to these located in tetrahedral sites (γ -type NiO)
254 [23].

255 Similar reduction traces were observed for MgO(x)-NiAl samples. Nevertheless,
256 significant changes in the H₂-TPR peaks positions and their relative contribution could
257 be noted. Table 2 summarises the H₂-TPR quantitative data extracted from the
258 integration of the Ni reduction bands. The reduction degree was also calculated as the
259 ratio between the measured H₂ uptake and theoretical H₂ amounts needed for a complete
260 reduction of Ni²⁺ ions. The analysis of the obtained results suggested that the reduction
261 of γ -type NiO species was strongly influenced by increased MgO amounts leading to
262 higher reduction temperatures (Figure 5). For instance, it shifted from 805 °C for the
263 MgO(0)-NiAl to 860 °C for the MgO(10)-NiAl catalyst. Furthermore, the progressive
264 addition of magnesia led to a decrease of the contribution of γ -type NiO species (from

265 42% for MgO(0)-NiAl to 26% for MgO(10)-NiAl) (Table 2). It is also relevant to
266 highlight that, at high temperatures ($> 860\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), the MgO-rich catalysts exhibited
267 additional reduction peaks which could be related to the reduction of Ni^{2+} in
268 $(\text{Mg,Ni})\text{Al}_2\text{O}_4$ mixed spinel [7, 32]. This Ni species (θ -type NiO) represented 4% and
269 10% of the total Ni reducible species in the MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl samples,
270 respectively. Regarding the effect of the addition of MgO on the reducibility of α -type
271 and β -type NiO species, the highest reduction peak temperatures were found for the
272 MgO(5)-NiAl catalyst, $525\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for α -type NiO and $750\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for β -type NiO (Figure 5). As
273 aforementioned this might be explained by a strong interaction of NiO with Mg species
274 resulting from a surface density close to that corresponding to a theoretical surface
275 monolayer.

276 Figure 4/Figure 5

277 3.1.4. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

278 The surface chemical composition and the Ni and Mg structures lying on the surface of
279 the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts were investigated by means of XPS techniques. Figure 6 (a)
280 displays the deconvoluted photoemission peaks for Ni $2p_{3/2}$ region. For all the analysed
281 samples the main XPS peak located in the range $855\text{-}856\text{ eV}$ and the shake-up satellite
282 peak in the range $861\text{-}862\text{ eV}$ showed that the Ni^{2+} ions were mainly incorporated in the
283 network of NiAl_2O_4 structure [5,23,32]. However, as reported in Table 3, the XPS peak
284 positions seemed to depend on the MgO content. For example, the MgO(5)-NiAl
285 catalyst showed the lowest Ni $2p_{3/2}$ peak binding energy (855.2 eV). This shift was
286 explained by an enrichment of the near surface of MgO(5)-NiAl sample with NiO [5,
287 23]. Moreover, as revealed by the FWHM data reported in Table 3, the MgO(5)-NiAl
288 sample showed the broadest Ni $2p_{3/2}$ peak (3.7 eV), thus suggesting a larger
289 heterogeneity in nickel environments. These observations were in good agreement with

290 the previously described H₂-TPR results which revealed that this sample exhibited,
291 besides the NiAl₂O₄ phase, the highest amount of α -type NiO species. Furthermore, a
292 parallel series of Mg 2p spectra was recorded for the MgO(x)-NiAl samples
293 (Figure 6 (b)). The value of O 1s level was taken as internal reference [33]. As seen in
294 Table 3 the Mg 2p main peak energy shifted from 50.1-50.2 eV for the MgO(x \leq 5)-
295 NiAl catalysts towards lower values for MgO-rich catalysts, MgO(7)-NiAl and
296 MgO(10)-NiAl (49.5 eV and 49.7 eV, respectively). In accordance with He et al. [34],
297 this trend was consistent with an increase of the Mg species film thickness from
298 submonolayer to multilayer coverage. Moreover, the comparison of the Mg 2p peak
299 energy for the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts with those corresponding to pure MgO and
300 MgAl₂O₄ (Table 3) evidenced the increase of MgAl₂O₄ phase contribution with MgO
301 loading which was in good agreement with the H₂-TPR data. Besides the main Mg 2p
302 peak the MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl spectra revealed the appearance of another
303 peak at a binding energy about 5 eV larger than the main peak. In several studies this
304 additional peak was associated with a growth of tridimensional Mg species which
305 formed islands with a critical size [35].

306 Table 3 also includes an estimation of Ni/Al and Mg/Al atomic ratios determined by
307 XPS for each catalyst and their comparison with those determined by WDXRF. It was
308 deduced that the Ni/Al XPS ratio remained almost constant for all the samples
309 (0.22-0.25), but it was lower by 50% with respect to that determined for the bulk
310 analysis (WDXRF). However, the comparison of the Mg/Al bulk ratios (0.06-0.25) with
311 the Mg/Al XPS ratios indicated an apparent enrichment of the near surface with Mg
312 species (0.07 for MgO(2.5)-NiAl, 0.1 for MgO(5)-NiAl, 0.24 for MgO(7)-NiAl and 0.4
313 for MgO(10)-NiAl).

314

Figure 6/Table 3

315 *3.1.5. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)*

316 The reduced MgO(x)-NiAl samples were investigated by transmission electron
317 microscopy (TEM). Figure 7 shows the MgO(x)-NiAl micrographs and the
318 corresponding size distribution histograms. The average Ni particle size was estimated
319 from an accumulated frequency including up to 95% of the total population. Table 2
320 also lists the values of the Ni dispersion and the metallic surface area (S_{Ni}) taking into
321 account the degree of reduction for each catalyst.

322 Examination of all the micrographs revealed the presence of Ni particles with a quasi
323 spherical shape. Nevertheless, the size distribution seemed to be affected by the MgO
324 addition. For the bare nickel aluminate, MgO(0)-NiAl, the distribution diagram
325 consisted of a broad asymmetric peak, including sizes ranged between 5 and 30 nm,
326 with an average size of 13 nm corresponding to a Ni dispersion of 7% (Table 2). By
327 contrast, a narrower and more symmetric distribution was observed in the case of the
328 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts thereby indicating an apparent homogeneity of the Ni particle
329 sizes. Furthermore, in agreement with XRD data, smaller Ni particle sizes were
330 deposited in all the MgO-containing samples (11-11.5 nm, $D = 8.7-9.4\%$), thereby
331 suggesting that the addition of magnesia inhibited the sintering of the metallic phase [7,
332 36-38]. Regarding the metallic surface area, it was observed that slightly higher values
333 were obtained for the MgO modified catalysts $14-15 \text{ m}^2_{Ni} \text{ g}^{-1}$ compared to the
334 Mg(0)-NiAl catalyst ($12 \text{ m}^2_{Ni} \text{ g}^{-1}$) (Table 2).

335 Figure 7

336 *3.1.6. Temperature programmed desorption of CO₂ (CO₂-TPD)*

337 The surface basicity of the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts was characterized by means
338 of CO₂-TPD techniques. Figure 8 (a) shows the corresponding desorption profiles
339 recorded on the samples after pre-adsorption of CO₂ at 40 °C for 1 h. The amounts of

340 desorbed CO₂ extracted from the integration of the bands centred at three temperature
341 ranges (40-150 °C, 150-350 °C and >350 °C) are reported in Table 4. Data
342 corresponding to bare alumina are also included for comparison. Generally, at low
343 temperatures the CO₂ desorption peaks are associated with the decomposition of
344 bicarbonates species adsorbed on the weak basic sites [39]. The second temperature
345 range corresponds to a decomposition of bidentate carbonates species which
346 characterise the medium-strength basic sites, while the desorption peaks at high
347 temperatures (> 350 °C) are assigned to the decomposition of unidentate carbonates
348 species formed on the strong basic sites.

349 It was found that the deposition of reduced Ni species onto the alumina surface
350 dramatically increased the total amount as well as the thermal stability of the adsorbed
351 CO₂ (Figure 8 (a) and Table 4). Indeed, the surface density of CO₂ desorbed from
352 alumina, 0.5 μmol m⁻², was much smaller than that determined for MgO(0)-NiAl,
353 2.7 μmol m⁻². However, the total amount of desorbed CO₂ notably decreased in the
354 magnesia doped catalysts. For example, it was about 1.5 μmol m⁻² for MgO(2.5)-NiAl,
355 1.9 μmol m⁻² for MgO(5)-NiAl and 1.2 μmol m⁻² for MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl.
356 This drop in the basic sites density with the MgO content might be related to the
357 structural evolution of Mg species lying on the surface. Indeed, our characterization
358 results pointed out a progressive enrichment of the catalysts with MgAl₂O₄ species with
359 MgO loading. In this sense, Cosimo et al. [39] found that in samples with Mg/Al < 1
360 segregation of bulk MgAl₂O₄ spinel occurred and caused a loss in the basic site density.
361 Table 4 also gives the distribution of the three types of surface basic sites classified
362 according to their strength. When compared to reduced nickel aluminate the distribution
363 appeared to be influenced by the deposition of MgO. It should be highlighted that,
364 among all the analysed samples, this effect was very strong on the MgO(5)-NiAl sample

365 which presented the lowest density of strong basic sites ($0.5 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$) and the highest
366 density of weak basic sites ($1 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$).

367 To facilitate their comparison the percentage of contribution of each group of basic sites
368 are displayed in Figure 8 (b). For the MgO(0)-NiAl sample the contribution of the
369 weak, medium and strong basic sites was 28.5%, 38.7% and 32.7%, respectively. By
370 contrast, the distribution on the MgO(2.5)-NiAl catalyst evidenced an increase in the
371 fraction of strong basic sites, which accounted for 73.2% of the total amount at the
372 expense of the medium-strength basic sites (5.3%). It was also observed a similar
373 distribution on the MgO-rich samples, MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl, thus
374 indicating that the nature of the active sites involved in the adsorption of CO_2 was
375 essentially the same on these two samples. The MgO(5)-NiAl sample presented a
376 distinct behaviour with a major contribution of weak basic sites which represented
377 52.8% of the total basic sites. This apparent weakening of the surface basic sites could
378 be related to the presence of large amounts of highly dispersed Mg species on the
379 surface.

380 Due to their relatively higher stability compared to weak basic sites a special attention
381 was paid to the relationship between the amounts of medium and strong basic sites
382 amounts and MgO loading. Figure 8 (c) displays the dependence of the density of basic
383 sites with this strength on the Mg/Al ratios determined by XPS (Table 3). The results
384 showed a significant loss in the surface basicity, respect to MgO(0)-NiAl sample
385 ($1.9 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$), with the abundance of Mg on the near surface up to a value of Mg/Al
386 corresponding to 0.1. For higher Mg/Al ratios the density of medium-strong basic sites
387 remained almost constant, about $0.85\text{-}0.9 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$. Then, the number of the sites
388 involved in the medium-strong basicity was essentially the same on all the over-
389 monolayer samples.

390

391 3.2. *Catalytic performance in the POM reaction*

392 In our previous study on the activity of Ni catalysts in the partial oxidation of methane
393 an indirect two-step mechanism based on total combustion at lower temperatures
394 followed by methane reforming by CO₂ and/or steam at high temperatures was verified.
395 Accordingly we found that at lower temperatures (<650 °C) very low CO/CO₂ ratios
396 were obtained thereby suggesting a high combustion activity and a low reforming
397 activity [23]. This poor reforming activity at low temperatures induced, moreover, was
398 related to drastic changes in the Ni oxidation state since inactive NiO was preferentially
399 formed. For this reason, the catalytic tests were carried out at high temperature (700 °C).

400 3.2.1. *Stoichiometric operating conditions (O/C = 1)*

401 Figure 9 (left) shows the evolution of methane conversion and H₂ yield with time on
402 stream at 700 °C and 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ over the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.
403 The activity data of a commercial RhAl catalyst was also included for the sake of
404 comparison. As a general behaviour, all the samples exhibited a marked stability in the
405 studied time on stream. Over the MgO-free nickel aluminate sample, MgO(0)-NiAl,
406 both high activity (75%) and H₂ yield (0.84) were found (Table 5). The addition of
407 2.5% of MgO seemed to provoke a significant decrease in its activity (71%) and the
408 yields of H₂ (0.76) and CO (0.62). However, the addition of MgO concentrations higher
409 than 2.5% induced an improvement of the catalytic performance. For instance, the
410 MgO(5)-NiAl catalyst proved the highest methane conversion (83%), close to that
411 attained by the rhodium catalyst and the thermodynamic equilibrium value (86%), and
412 the highest yields of H₂ and CO (0.92 and 0.75, respectively) whereas it exhibited the
413 lowest yield of CO₂ (0.08). According to their catalytic activity and H₂ yield the
414 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts followed this trend: MgO(5)-NiAl > MgO(7)-NiAl >

415 MgO(10)-NiAl > MgO(0)-NiAl > MgO(2.5)-NiAl. On another hand, it should be noted
416 that the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts demonstrated a relatively good resistance against the
417 coke formation which was lower than 7.3% (Table 5).

418 Figure 9/Table 5

419 The spent catalysts were analysed by XRD in order to determine the nature of deposited
420 carbon and to evaluate the Ni particle sizes. The patterns of the post-run samples
421 (not displayed) showed the appearance of graphitic carbon phase with low intensity
422 signals. On the other hand, the Ni particle sizes estimated by means of Scherrer equation
423 showed generally slight changes (Table 2). Among all the used catalysts the
424 MgO(2.5)-NiAl catalyst presented the largest particle growth (from 9.5 nm to 13 nm).
425 Table 5 also lists the measured H₂/CO and CO/CO₂ ratios. The H₂/CO ratios over the
426 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts were in all the cases around 2.7-2.9. These relatively high
427 values (> 2) could explain the high stability of the catalysts due to the
428 non-encapsulation of the metal particles by deposited carbon [40]. In our previous study
429 on the performance of the Ni/alumina in the partial oxidation of methane we reported
430 that an increase in active metal dispersion led to higher H₂/CO ratios and an enhanced
431 stability of the catalysts [23]. Accordingly, the similar dispersion of Ni particles, in the
432 7-9% range, on the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts could explain the similar obtained H₂/CO
433 ratio values. However, the analysis of the CO/CO₂ ratio values, ranged between 6.2 and
434 9.6, revealed significant differences among the samples. Generally, the production of
435 CO₂ is related to the occurrence of CO disproportionation and/or methane total
436 oxidation reactions [23]. The gasification of deposited carbon by the produced water (as
437 a product of CH₄ combustion) is one of the reasons that might explain the low carbon
438 deposition detected on the used catalysts.

439 Since no marked differences were observed in the dispersion of metallic nickel among
440 all the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts a special attention was devoted to an examination of the
441 influence of structural and chemical properties induced by the Mg species on their
442 catalytic properties. Figure 10 shows the influence of the strong basic sites density
443 measured by CO₂-TPD on the activity (X(CH₄)) and the product distribution (Y(H₂) and
444 CO/CO₂ ratio). The results showed a clear correlation between the surface chemical
445 properties and the catalytic properties of the samples since revealed a decrease in
446 methane conversion and H₂ yields with increasing density of strong basic sites.
447 Furthermore, the dependence trace of CO/CO₂ ratio on the strong basic sites density
448 showed that the reforming activity was governed by the density of strong basic sites.
449 Hence, the sample presenting the lowest strong basic sites density,
450 MgO(5)-NiAl, exhibited the highest reforming activity.

451 According to Cosimo et al. [39] the strong basic sites that presented high stability
452 predominantly consisted of O²⁻ anions. Moreover, in their study on the mechanism of
453 the POM over a Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst Jin et al. [41] established that the surface intermediate
454 Ni-C species could react with two types of oxygen species. The first oxygen species
455 named mobile was a product of the activation of oxygen which could react with Ni-C
456 species to produce CO whereas the second species consisted of chemisorbed O²⁻ species
457 which reacted with Ni-C species to produce CO₂. These data could explain the
458 difference observed in the catalytic behaviour of our investigated materials. The
459 observed decrease in the CO/CO₂ ratio with the increase of strong basic density could
460 be associated with the increased amounts of O²⁻ ions which could enhance the formation
461 of CO₂ at the expense of the CO formation.

462 Figure 10

463 3.2.2. *Non-stoichiometric operating conditions (O/C = 0.75)*

464 In order to examine the stability of the prepared MgO(x)-NiAl samples catalytic runs
465 under more severe conditions were conducted with a higher volume hourly space
466 velocity, namely $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$, and a lower O/C molar ratio (from 1 to 0.75)
467 (Figure 9 (right)). As expected, the selected conditions provoked a decrease in the initial
468 activity of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts and an apparent deactivation with time on stream.
469 The amount of deposited carbon was larger than 24 wt.% for all the used catalysts
470 suggesting that the observed deactivation was essentially associated with poisoning of
471 active sites by coke precursors. For instance, the initial methane conversion over the
472 MgO(5)-NiAl catalyst was around 65% (versus 83% obtained with O/C = 1). Even so it
473 kept its superior behaviour compared to the rest of the catalysts. In line with the
474 catalytic results under softer conditions, the initial methane conversion over the studied
475 catalysts seemed to have a similar correlation with the density of strong basic sites
476 densities discussed above. Indeed, it decreased from 65% for the catalyst with the
477 lowest strong sites density, MgO(5)-NiAl, to 54% over the catalyst with the highest
478 strong sites density, MgO(2.5)-NiAl. It should be highlighted that, under non-
479 stoichiometric operating conditions (O/C = 0.75), the MgO addition seemed to improve
480 the resistance against sintering (Table 2). For instance, the Ni particle size on the
481 MgO(0)-NiAl catalyst increased from 9 to 17.5 nm while it did not reach 15 nm on all
482 the Mg catalysts.

483 Figure 11 shows the dependence of the activity loss (%), evaluated as the difference
484 between initial conversion and conversion at 20 h divided by the initial conversion, on
485 the MgO loading. For the bare sample, MgO(0)-NiAl, the activity decreased by 5%. The
486 loss of activity upon increasing the MgO content seemed to depend on the differences in
487 the textural properties among the tested catalysts. The addition of an amount of MgO

488 lower than the theoretical monolayer dispersion value improved the stability of the
489 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts. By contrast, the catalysts with an over-monolayer MgO
490 amounts exhibited a poorer stability when compared to the MgO-free sample. In
491 accordance with our characterisation results it could be concluded that the highly
492 dispersed Mg species enhanced the stability of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts whereas an
493 enrichment of the surface with the over-monolayer Mg species accelerated the
494 deactivation of the catalysts.

495 Figure 11

496 Given the promising behaviour of MgO(5)-NiAl its performance was evaluated for a
497 considerably more prolonged reaction time interval (75 h) (Figure 12). For comparison
498 the MgO(7)-NiAl catalyst was also investigated. The results showed that despite the
499 comparable amounts of deposited carbon (64-68 wt.%) and Ni particle sizes (20-21 nm)
500 the MgO(5)-NiAl catalyst maintained its superiority in terms of catalytic performance
501 and stability with respect to the MgO(7)-NiAl catalyst (Table 5). This comparison
502 meant that the catalytic performance differences in the POM reaction were not a
503 function of the active nickel state (dispersion and the corresponding deposited carbon
504 amounts). This might point out, however, that the improved structural and chemical
505 properties provided by the highly dispersed Mg species played a key role in the
506 enhancement of the activity and the stability of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts in the POM
507 reaction.

508 Figure 12

509

510 4. Conclusions

511 Bulk nickel aluminate spinel (NiAl_2O_4) was synthesised by precipitation and
512 subsequently loaded with varying amounts of MgO (2.5-10 wt.%). The samples in both

513 calcined and reduced catalysts were thoroughly characterised by a wide number of
514 analytical techniques including BET, XRD, H₂-TPR, XPS, TEM and CO₂-TPD. By
515 combining the information obtained from all these studies, a detailed description of the
516 texture, structure, Mg and Ni distribution and chemical properties of the catalysts could
517 be proposed.

518 The addition of magnesia to the nickel aluminate spinel induced the formation of nickel
519 species with different chemical nature, namely NiO-MgO solid solution, mixed
520 (Ni,Mg)Al₂O₄ spinel and relatively hardly reducible NiO and NiAl₂O₄ phases. In
521 contrast to the calcined samples, the formation of MgAl₂O₄ was much more pronounced
522 on the reduced samples because of the presence of large amounts of the alumina as a
523 consequence of the reduction of nickel aluminate, which subsequently interact with
524 MgO to form MgAl₂O₄ phase. Moreover, on the MgO doped catalysts the metallic
525 nickel particles exhibited a slightly higher resistance to sintering compared to those
526 derived from the bare NiAl₂O₄ spinel. In addition, the presence of magnesium species
527 also provoked drastic changes in the number of surface basic sites and their distribution,
528 which could be modulated by modifying the MgO content.

529 The catalytic behaviour of the reduced samples was investigated in the partial oxidation
530 of methane. The results showed that the modification of NiAl₂O₄ by MgO with a
531 concentration higher than 2.5 wt.% clearly enhanced its catalytic performance which
532 was close to that of a commercial Rh catalyst. It was also found that the reforming
533 efficiency (conversion, H₂ yield and stability) could be tuned by controlling the surface
534 strong basic sites density. The MgO(5)-NiAl sample with a magnesium loading close to
535 the theoretical monolayer exhibited the lower density of strong basic sites and the best
536 catalytic performance.

537

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- 619

620 **CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES**

621 Table 1. Elemental analysis and textural properties of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

622 Table 2 Reducibility and structural properties of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

623 Table 3 XPS study of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

624 Table 4 Surface basic sites properties as determined by CO₂-TPD study.

625 Table 5 Catalytic performance of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts in the POM reaction.

626

627 Figure 1 Pore sizes distribution for the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

628 Figure 2 XRD patterns of the (a) calcined and (b) reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

629 Figure 3 Correlation between the lattice parameter corresponding to γ -alumina and
630 the Mg/Al molar ratios as determined by WDXRF.

631 Figure 4 H₂-TPR profiles of the calcined MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

632 Figure 5 Dependence of the reduction peak temperatures on the MgO loading for the
633 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

634 Figure 6 XPS spectra for the (a) Ni 2p_{3/2} and (b) Mg 2p regions of the calcined
635 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

636 Figure 7 TEM images and Ni particle sizes distribution of the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl
637 catalysts.

638 Figure 8 (a) CO₂-TPD profiles of the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts, (b) the
639 contribution of each basic sites strength group and (c) the dependence of the
640 density of the medium-strong surface basic sites on the Mg/Al XPS ratios.

641 Figure 9 Catalytic performance in terms of CH₄ conversion and hydrogen yield as a
642 function of time. Reaction conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹;
643 10%CH₄/5%O₂/85%N₂; W = 0.125 g; 700 °C; 20 h (left) and

644 $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; 15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂; W = 0.125 g; 700 °C;
645 20 h (right).

646 Figure 10 The influence of the strong basic sites density measured by CO₂-TPD on the
647 activity (X(CH₄),%) and the product distribution (Y(H₂) and CO/CO₂ ratio).
648 Reaction conditions: $38400 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; 10%CH₄/5%O₂/85%N₂;
649 W = 0.125 g; 700 °C; 20 h.

650 Figure 11 Dependence of the activity loss (%) in non-stoichiometric conditions
651 (O/C = 0.75) on the MgO loadings.

652 Figure 12 Stability performance in terms of CH₄ conversion and hydrogen yield over
653 MgO(5)-NiAl and MgO(7)-NiAl catalysts as a function of time. Reaction
654 conditions: $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; 15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂;
655 W = 0.125 g; 700 °C; 75 h.

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657

658

Catalysts	Ni, wt.% ^(a)	MgO, wt.% ^(a)	S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	W _p , nm	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹
MgO(0)-NiAl	(32.1)	(0)	67 (75)	14.4 (12.7)	0.32 (0.30)
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	(31.5)	(2.4)	64 (68)	14.5 (12.9)	0.29 (0.29)
MgO(5)-NiAl	(31)	(4.9)	62 (62)	15 (13.8)	0.29 (0.28)
MgO(7)-NiAl	(30.4)	(7)	59 (61)	15.5 (13.9)	0.28 (0.28)
MgO(10)-NiAl	(29.7)	(10)	59 (59)	16.6 (15.4)	0.31 (0.28)

Values in brackets correspond to the calcined catalysts.

^(a)Determined by WDXRF

659

660

Table 1

Catalysts	H ₂ -TPR					TEM				XRD (Ni ⁰ particle size, nm)		
	H ₂ uptake, mmol g ⁻¹	Relative amount of NiO species, % ^(a)				Reduction degree, %	Ni ⁰ particle size, nm	D, % ^(b)	S _{Ni} ^(c) , m ² _{Ni} g ⁻¹	Reduced catalysts	Spent catalysts ^(d)	Spent catalysts ^(e)
		α	β	γ	θ							
MgO(0)-NiAl	5.6	19 (490)	39 (720)	42 (805)	0	100	13	7.0	12	11	9.	18
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	5.6	22 (480)	40 (740)	38 (815)	0	100	11	8.9	15	9.5	13	14
MgO(5)-NiAl	5.1	25 (525)	40 (750)	35 (825)	0	100	11.5	8.7	15	9	12	13.5
MgO(7)-NiAl	5.2	12 (480)	59 (720)	25 (835)	4 (>860)	100	11	9.4	15	9	11	15
MgO(10)-NiAl	4.7	16 (505)	49 (715)	26 (860)	10 (>860)	94	11	8.7	14	9	9	13

^(a)Values in brackets correspond to the peak temperature (°C) of each reduction band.

^(b)Ni dispersion taking into account the extent of reduction at 850 °C.

^(c)Metallic surface area taking into account the extent of reduction at 850 °C.

^(d)Reaction conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 10%CH₄/5%O₂/85%N₂; 700 °C; 20 h.

^(e)Reaction conditions: 60000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂; 700 °C; 20 h.

661

662

Table 2

663

Catalysts	Main Ni 2p _{3/2} , eV	FWHM main Ni 2p _{3/2} , eV	Main Mg 2p, eV	Main O 1s, eV	Ni/Al	Mg/Al	Ni/Al ^(a)	Mg/Al ^(a)
MgO(0)-NiAl	855.7	3.5	-	530.6	0.22	0.00	0.50	0.00
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	855.6	3.0	50.1	530.6	0.24	0.07	0.51	0.06
MgO(5)-NiAl	855.2	3.7	50.2	530.3	0.25	0.10	0.50	0.11
MgO(7)-NiAl	855.4	3.4	49.5	530.4	0.22	0.24	0.51	0.17
MgO(10)-NiAl	855.6	3.4	49.7	530.0	0.25	0.40	0.51	0.25
MgO	-	-	50.4	-	-	-	-	-
MgAl ₂ O ₄	-	-	49.4	-	-	-	-	-

^(a)Determined by WDXRF.

664

665

Table 3

666

Catalysts	Total surface basic sites density, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$	Weak basic sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$	Medium-strength basic sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$	Strong basic sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$
$\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$	0.5	0.16	0.21	0.13
MgO(0)-NiAl	2.7	0.77	1.04	0.88
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	1.5	0.32	0.08	1.10
MgO(5)-NiAl	1.9	1.00	0.40	0.50
MgO(7)-NiAl	1.2	0.33	0.24	0.64
MgO(10)-NiAl	1.2	0.38	0.18	0.64

667

668

Table 4

Catalysts	X(CH ₄), %	Y(H ₂)	Y(CO)	Y(CO ₂)	H ₂ /CO	CO/CO ₂	Coke, wt. %
Equilibrium	86	0.92	0.81	0.06	2.3	14.6	-
MgO(0)-NiAl	75	0.84	0.65	0.1	2.8	6.2	2.8
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	71	0.76	0.62	0.09	2.7	6.6	7.3
MgO(5)-NiAl	83	0.92	0.75	0.08	2.8	9.6	5.7
MgO(7)-NiAl	78	0.90	0.68	0.1	2.9	7.2	0.7
MgO(10)-NiAl	77	0.87	0.68	0.09	2.8	7.5	6.5
RhAl	86	0.66	0.77	0.09	1.7	8.8	1.7

Reaction conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 10%CH₄/5%O₂/85%N₂; W = 0.125 g; 700 °C; 20 h

Catalysts	X(CH ₄), %	Y(H ₂)	Y(CO)	Y(CO ₂)	H ₂ /CO	CO/CO ₂	Coke, wt. %
Equilibrium	62	0.90	0.58	0.04	3.1	13.7	-
MgO(0)-NiAl	57	0.41	0.49	0.08	1.7	6.3	43
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	54	0.37	0.44	0.10	1.7	4.6	24
MgO(5)-NiAl	63	0.46	0.56	0.07	1.7	7.8	47
MgO(7)-NiAl	59	0.43	0.51	0.08	1.7	6.7	31
MgO(10)-NiAl	53	0.39	0.43	0.10	1.8	4.3	40
RhAl	61	0.45	0.55	0.07	1.6	8.1	2
MgO(5)-NiAl (75 h)	60	0.45	0.53	0.07	1.7	7.5	68
MgO(7)-NiAl (75 h)	56	0.42	0.47	0.09	1.8	5.4	64

Reaction conditions: 60000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂; W=0.125 g; 700 °C; 20 h/75 h

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Table 5

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 11

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Figure 12

ZTF-FCT
Zientzia eta Teknologia Fakultatea
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HIGHLIGHTS – BULLET POINTS

MgO/NiAl₂O₄ catalysts were prepared by precipitation followed by wet-impregnation.

The influence of the MgO loading on chemical and structural properties was examined.

Highly dispersed Mg species promoted the partial oxidation of methane.

The deposition of MgO enhanced the resistance against metallic nickel sintering.

An optimum 5wt.%MgO loading resulted in the lowest strong basicity.

1 **MgO/NiAl₂O₄ AS A NEW FORMULATION OF REFORMING**
2 **CATALYSTS. TUNING THE SURFACE PROPERTIES FOR THE**
3 **ENHANCED PARTIAL OXIDATION OF METHANE**

4

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21

22 **Abstract**

23 Magnesia modified nickel aluminate spinel catalysts were synthesised and characterised
24 by BET, TEM, XRD, H₂-TPR, XPS, CO₂-TPD and TGA-MS techniques. The addition
25 of this promoter induced significant changes in the textural, structural and chemical
26 properties of the resulting spinel derived catalysts. Thus, it enhanced the resistance of
27 the deposited Ni particles against sintering, whereas, upon increasing MgO loading, it
28 drastically modified the density and the strength of the surface basic sites. In fact, an
29 apparent weakening of the surface basic sites with the abundance of highly dispersed
30 Mg species was interestingly observed.

31 The changes provoked by MgO addition deeply influenced the catalytic performance of
32 the prepared samples in the partial oxidation of methane reaction at 700 °C. In this
33 sense, it was found a good correlation between the measured density of the strong basic
34 sites on the different samples, including the bare NiAl₂O₄, and their catalytic activity.
35 Hence, the MgO(5 wt.)/NiAl₂O₄ sample, with a magnesium loading close to the
36 theoretical monolayer and the lowest strong basic density sites, exhibited the best
37 catalytic performance under both stoichiometric (O/C = 1) and non-stoichiometric
38 (O/C = 0.75) conditions during a relatively prolonged time on stream.

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40

41 *Keywords:* Nickel aluminate, magnesium oxide, surface basicity, partial oxidation of
42 methane

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46 1. Introduction

47 The application of energy technology based on hydrogen as energy vector is a
48 promising alternative, to traditional fossil fuels combustions, which could facilitate the
49 transition to a sustainable development of clean energy systems [1-3]. Nowadays,
50 hydrogen is mostly produced via steam reforming of methane (SRM, Ec. (1)).
51 Nevertheless, this process is relatively expensive due to its high endothermicity [4, 5].
52 For this reason the partial oxidation of methane (POM, Ec. (2)) is often viewed as a
53 more advantageous strategy since the process needs a lower energy input due to its mild
54 exothermicity, which reduces operation costs. Thus, the technology does not need an
55 external fired heater which makes it simpler and more practical for small reactors used
56 in mobile applications [6-9]. Furthermore, the POM is a good option when the posterior
57 use of the syngas stream requires a suitable H₂/CO ratio. Nevertheless, there are many
58 parallel reactions that could occur during the POM process, such as water gas shift
59 reaction (WGS, Ec. (3)) and/or methane total oxidation (Ec. (4)), which produce
60 significant amounts of carbon dioxide in the product gas [10-12].

65 It is known that noble metals, such as Rh and Pt, exhibit a good reforming activity and
66 high resistance against carbon formation. However, this high cost limits their utilisation.
67 As a result, research is extensively focused on other promising substitutes based on
68 active transition metals [11, 13-15]. Among the non-noble metals, Ni-based catalysts
69 have similar activity compared to those based on noble metals [9, 13, 16, 17].
70 Nevertheless, they are very sensitive to the structural changes that can affect their active

71 species under the severe conditions of the preparation (reduction at high temperatures)
72 and during the reforming catalytic process. According to many authors these changes
73 may provoke decay in their activity and stability [16-22]. In this sense, many efforts
74 have been devoted to develop active and stable catalysts (minimizing sintering and
75 coking) by optimising the preparation route to achieve high nickel dispersion. In this
76 sense, the literature proposes some strategies based on the preparation of spinel
77 (NiM_2O_4) [18, 19] or perovskite (MNiO_3) [20-22] phases as catalyst precursors, where
78 nickel is stabilised in a well-defined structure. For instance, in our previous studies we
79 demonstrated that the NiAl_2O_4 spinel materials, reduced at high temperature (850 °C),
80 led to a formation of metallic nickel supported on alumina surface with high dispersion
81 and relatively small crystallite size [13, 23]. These synthesised catalysts proved high
82 activity, selectivity and stability in various methane reforming reactions, compared to
83 those prepared by conventional routes.

84 Also, within the objective to improve activity and stability of Ni catalysts, by reducing
85 the Ni crystallites sizes and their stabilisation against sintering, the effect of the addition
86 of some alkali and alkaline earth metals used as chemical promoters has been
87 extensively investigated [8, 24-26]. For instance, Sousa et al. [27] studied the
88 relationship between structure and deactivation in the dry reforming of methane over
89 Ni/alumina doped with CeO_2 , MgO , ZrO_2 and La_2O_3 catalysts. Their results showed that
90 the catalyst promoted with MgO exhibited the highest performance amongst all the
91 investigated materials. This behaviour was explained by a synergetic effect between
92 nickel species and $\text{MgAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4$ structures which enhanced the resistance to
93 structural transformations and inhibited carbon formation. By contrast, Kirillov et al. [9]
94 observed some structural changes on Ni/ MgO /alumina catalysts used in partial
95 oxidation of methane for 100 h, but this was not at the expense of their activity. Besides

96 its promotional effect on the structural properties of Ni catalysts many investigations
97 highlighted the suitable surface basicity provided by MgO promoter which greatly
98 influences the adsorption-desorption of reaction intermediates and thus the catalytic
99 reforming performance [28].

100 The major objective of this work is the analysis of textural, chemical and structural
101 properties and catalytic behaviour of a set of nickel aluminate samples with varying the
102 amount of MgO promoter. The choice of the magnesia loading in the 2.5-10 wt.% range
103 has been made in accordance with the BET surface area of the prepared catalysts to
104 obtain surface Mg densities ranging from sub-monolayer to over-monolayer values. It
105 should be noted that, to our knowledge, the modification of NiAl₂O₄ spinel materials
106 with MgO, their characterisation and their catalytic performance in the POM reaction
107 have not been yet investigated. Special attention has been devoted to the influence of
108 MgO loading on the physico-chemical and catalytic properties of the reduced
109 MgO/NiAl₂O₄ samples.

110

111 **2. Experimental**

112 *2.1. Catalysts preparation*

113 Bulk NiAl₂O₄ (MgO(0)-NiAl sample) was synthesised from a mixture of two aqueous
114 solutions Ni(CH₃-COO)₂·4H₂O and Al(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, with the desired 1:2 Ni/Al molar
115 ratio. The final pH of the aqueous solution was adjusted at 8 by adding aqueous
116 ammonia (0.6 M). The precipitate was subsequently aged for 30 minutes before being
117 filtered and washed with hot deionised water. Afterwards the recovered solid was dried
118 at 110 °C overnight and then calcined at 850 °C in static air for 4 h at a heating rate of
119 10 °C min⁻¹ [23].

120 The incorporation of magnesium oxide on the nickel aluminate (3 g) was carried out by
121 wet impregnation with an aqueous solution of $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The samples were dried
122 at 110 °C overnight and then calcined at 850 °C in static air for 2 h using a heating rate
123 of 10 °C min^{-1} . The catalysts were labelled $\text{MgO}(2.5)\text{-NiAl}$, $\text{MgO}(5)\text{-NiAl}$, $\text{MgO}(7)\text{-}$
124 NiAl and $\text{MgO}(10)\text{-NiAl}$, which corresponded to MgO loadings of 2.5, 5, 7 and
125 10 wt.%, respectively. NiO and MgO pure oxides were prepared by simple calcination
126 at 850 °C in air of nickel acetate and magnesium nitrate, respectively. Referring to the
127 MgAl_2O_4 sample was obtained commercially from Sigma-Aldrich.

128 2.2. Catalyst characterisation

129 The catalysts were characterised by N_2 physisorption at -196 °C, wavelength dispersive
130 X-ray fluorescence (WDXRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), temperature programmed
131 reduction with hydrogen ($\text{H}_2\text{-TPR}$), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS),
132 transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and temperature programmed desorption of
133 CO_2 ($\text{CO}_2\text{-TPD}$). The experimental details of each analytical technique were described
134 elsewhere [13, 23].

135 Additionally, the surface basicity of the reduced samples was characterised by
136 temperature programmed desorption of CO_2 techniques ($\text{CO}_2\text{-TPD}$). These studies were
137 carried out on an experimental setup coupled to a MKS Cirrus LM99 mass
138 spectrometer. Prior to running the TPD experiments, the oxide samples (200 mg) were
139 submitted to a pre-treatment routine consisting of a reduction step at 850 °C (2 h) in a
140 flow 5% H_2/Ar , cooling to 40 °C in a flow of He, treatment in a flow of CO_2/He for 1 h
141 at 40 °C, and finally 1 h under flowing He, also at 40 °C. The thermo desorption of CO_2
142 step was carried out under He flow rate of 50 $\text{cm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$ and a heating ramp of
143 10 °C min^{-1} (up to 900 °C).

144 The spent samples were characterised by S_{BET} measurements, XRD, TEM and
145 thermogravimetry coupled to mass spectrometry (TGA-MS).

146 2.3. Catalytic tests

147 Catalytic tests were performed in a bench-scale fixed-bed reactor (Microactivity
148 modular laboratory system provided by PID Eng&Tech S.L) operated at atmospheric
149 pressure and fully monitored by computer. The reactor was made of stainless steel with
150 an internal diameter of 9 mm and a height of 305 mm, in which the temperature was
151 controlled by a thermocouple placed in the catalyst bed. Typically 0.125 g of catalyst in
152 powdered form (0.3-0.5 mm) was loaded. The catalysts bed was diluted with inert
153 quartz 1:1 (1-1.25 mm). Different experiments were carried out to evaluate the catalytic
154 activity and stability of the samples. Firstly, a feed gas mixture containing 10%CH₄,
155 5%O₂ (O/C = 1) and balanced with N₂ was used. Hence, a volume hourly space velocity
156 at 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ was maintained using Bronkhorst mass flow controllers.
157 Before the reaction, the catalyst was reduced *in situ* under 5%H₂/N₂ at 850 °C for 2 h.
158 The experiments were carried out at constant temperature (700 °C) for about 20 h.
159 The catalysts were also intentionally run under more severe conditions to allow
160 meaningful reactivity and stability comparison. Thus, maintaining the same time on
161 stream (20 h) and operation temperature (700 °C), the volume hourly space velocity at
162 60000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ (15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂) was increased while the O/C mole
163 ratio was lowered down to 0.75. Additional experiments were conducted over a more
164 prolonged time on line (75 h).

165 On basis of the dry molar flow at the inlet and outlet of the reactor, conversion and
166 product yields were calculated, according to the following equations:

$$167 \quad X(\text{CH}_4), \% = \frac{F_{\text{out}}(\text{CO}) + F_{\text{out}}(\text{CO}_2)}{F_{\text{in}}(\text{CH}_4)} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

168
$$Y(H_2) = \frac{F_{out}(H_2)}{2 \cdot F_{in}(CH_4)} \quad (6)$$

169
$$Y(CO) = \frac{F_{out}(CO)}{F_{in}(CH_4)} \quad (7)$$

170
$$Y(CO_2) = \frac{F_{out}(CO_2)}{F_{in}(CH_4)} \quad (8)$$

171

172 **3. Results and discussion**

173 *3.1. Characterisation of the fresh samples*

174 *3.1.1. N₂-physorption (BET measurements)*

175 The textural properties of the calcined and reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts were
176 examined by nitrogen adsorption-desorption measurements. All the samples exhibited
177 IV-type isotherms, indicating the existence of well-developed mesopores, with
178 significantly reduced hysteresis loops (not shown). The corresponding specific surface
179 area values are reported in Table 1. The magnesia unmodified catalyst (MgO(0)-NiAl)
180 presented a specific surface area of 75 m² g⁻¹. Upon addition of MgO the surface area
181 significantly decreased. Hence, for MgO-rich samples it was 61 m² g⁻¹ for
182 MgO(7)-NiAl and 59 m² g⁻¹ for MgO(10)-NiAl.

183 The reduction of the MgO(0)-NiAl catalyst provoked a significant drop (about 10%) in
184 its specific surface area, from 75 to 67 m² g⁻¹. However, this loss of surface area
185 associated with the phase transformation from NiAl₂O₄ to Ni/Al₂O₃ was less evident in
186 the presence of increased amounts of Mg. Thus, this resistance against the decrease of
187 surface area was notably enhanced with MgO loading. For instance, the reduction of the
188 sample with the highest MgO loading, MgO(10)-NiAl, did not affect its specific surface
189 area (59 m² g⁻¹).

190 Figure 1 shows the pore size distributions of the reduced samples. The shape of the
191 traces of the samples with a low MgO loading ($\leq 5\%$) looked similar. Their distribution
192 were, thus, characterised by a main peak centred at approximately 18 nm and a shoulder
193 at 14 nm. However, for higher MgO loadings ($\geq 7\%$) the pore sizes had a unimodal
194 distribution located at 18 nm, thereby revealing the absence of narrower pores peak
195 (at 14 nm). Since the surface density of Mg atoms in the MgO(5)-NiAl sample was
196 11.8 at. nm^{-2} , very close to the theoretical surface monolayer, 12.4 at. nm^{-2} , we might
197 reasonably conclude that most of narrow pores of MgO-rich samples were completely
198 filled by the over-monolayer Mg species.

199 Table 1/Figure 1

200 3.1.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

201 The MgO(x)-NiAl samples were also characterised by means of X-ray powder
202 diffraction in order to investigate the effect of the MgO addition on their structural
203 properties. Figure 2 compares the XRD patterns for all the prepared MgO(x)-NiAl in
204 their calcined (850 °C) and reduced (850 °C) states (Figure 2 (a) and Figure 2 (b),
205 respectively). The crystalline phases were identified using the JCPDS files. Expectedly
206 the calcined MgO(0)-NiAl sample displayed a set of diffraction peaks centred at
207 $2\theta = 19.3^\circ, 31.5^\circ, 37.2^\circ, 45.2^\circ, 59.9^\circ$ and 65.7° , assignable to the nickel aluminate phase
208 (JCPDS 78-1601) [29]. Furthermore, the MgO(0)-NiAl diffractogram showed additional
209 peaks associated with NiO structure, at 43.6° and 62.9° (JCPDS 89-7131). It should be
210 noted that the XRD patterns of the calcined MgO catalysts showed a significant
211 evolution of the NiO diffraction peaks which shifted to lower angles. This effect was
212 more pronounced on the MgO-rich samples. For instance, 2θ angle shifted from 43.6°
213 for MgO(0)-NiAl sample to 43.5° and 43.4° for MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl,
214 respectively. These observations suggested the diffusion of Mg^{2+} cations in NiO crystal

215 lattice to form MgO-NiO solid solution [26]. Moreover, the slight shift might be
216 explained by the identical structures of NiO and MgO phases and their very close lattice
217 parameters.

218 Figure 2 (b) includes the diffractograms of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts after reduction at
219 850 °C. As expected, the MgO(0)-NiAl pattern showed a transformation of nickel
220 aluminate and NiO structures into gamma alumina (JCPDS 79-1558) and metallic
221 nickel (JCPDS 89-7128) phases. Apparently, no diffraction peaks associated with NiO
222 or MgO were visible in the patterns of MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts. However, because of its
223 high formation heat, above 420 kJ mol^{-1} , the reduction of magnesium oxide under the
224 used reduction conditions (850 °C for 2 h) was ruled out. Then, the structural changes of
225 Mg species provoked by the reduction process were followed by assessing the
226 diffraction lines attributed to gamma alumina which seemed to shift to lower angles
227 with MgO. Figure 3 shows a correlation between the lattice parameter corresponding to
228 gamma alumina structure and the Mg/Al molar ratios determined by WDXRF, for all
229 the reduced samples and for pure MgAl₂O₄ used as reference. The results clearly
230 indicated a shift of the lattice parameter (a) towards higher values with MgO loading,
231 thereby suggesting a progressive formation of MgAl₂O₄. In their study on NiSn/MgO-
232 Al₂O₃ materials Penkova et al. [30] attributed this shift to the formation of magnesium
233 aluminate phase. In this sense Jacob et al. [31] also reported that the formation of
234 MgAl₂O₄ from MgO and Al₂O₃ could start at around 800 °C.

235 The average size of Ni particles calculated by Scherrer equation was found to be around
236 11 nm on the MgO(0)-NiAl catalyst while somewhat smaller particles with an average
237 size of about 9-9.5 nm were detected for the magnesia modified catalysts (Table 2). We
238 might conclude that the deposition of MgO enhanced the resistance against metallic
239 nickel sintering.

240

241 *3.1.3. Temperature programmed reduction (H₂-TPR)*

242 The H₂-TPR experiments were performed in order to identify the various Ni reducible
243 species and the influence of MgO on the reducibility of the calcined MgO(x)-NiAl
244 samples (Figure 4). It should be noted that no reduction peaks were detected on the
245 H₂-TPR profiles of MgAl₂O₄ and MgO samples used as reference (not displayed). The
246 H₂-TPR curve of MgO(0)-NiAl sample exhibited a typical profile of non-stoichiometric
247 nickel aluminate materials. This exhibited three reduction peaks centred at 490, 720 and
248 805 °C. The former, α -type NiO, was attributed to the reduction of NiO species which
249 had strong interaction with the spinel phase. The two high-temperature reduction peaks
250 at 720 and 805 °C were associated with the reduction of the Ni²⁺ species incorporated in
251 an inverse nickel aluminate structure. In our previous study we proved that, in an
252 inverse spinel structure, the Ni²⁺ ions located in octahedral sites (β -type NiO) were
253 more prone to be reduced compared to these located in tetrahedral sites (γ -type NiO)
254 [23].

255 Similar reduction traces were observed for MgO(x)-NiAl samples. Nevertheless,
256 significant changes in the H₂-TPR peaks positions and their relative contribution could
257 be noted. Table 2 summarises the H₂-TPR quantitative data extracted from the
258 integration of the Ni reduction bands. The reduction degree was also calculated as the
259 ratio between the measured H₂ uptake and theoretical H₂ amounts needed for a complete
260 reduction of Ni²⁺ ions. The analysis of the obtained results suggested that the reduction
261 of γ -type NiO species was strongly influenced by increased MgO amounts leading to
262 higher reduction temperatures (Figure 5). For instance, it shifted from 805 °C for the
263 MgO(0)-NiAl to 860 °C for the MgO(10)-NiAl catalyst. Furthermore, the progressive
264 addition of magnesia led to a decrease of the contribution of γ -type NiO species (from

265 42% for MgO(0)-NiAl to 26% for MgO(10)-NiAl) (Table 2). It is also relevant to
266 highlight that, at high temperatures ($> 860\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), the MgO-rich catalysts exhibited
267 additional reduction peaks which could be related to the reduction of Ni^{2+} in
268 $(\text{Mg,Ni})\text{Al}_2\text{O}_4$ mixed spinel [7, 32]. This Ni species (θ -type NiO) represented 4% and
269 10% of the total Ni reducible species in the MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl samples,
270 respectively. Regarding the effect of the addition of MgO on the reducibility of α -type
271 and β -type NiO species, the highest reduction peak temperatures were found for the
272 MgO(5)-NiAl catalyst, $525\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for α -type NiO and $750\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for β -type NiO (Figure 5). As
273 aforementioned this might be explained by a strong interaction of NiO with Mg species
274 resulting from a surface density close to that corresponding to a theoretical surface
275 monolayer.

276 Figure 4/Figure 5

277 3.1.4. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

278 The surface chemical composition and the Ni and Mg structures lying on the surface of
279 the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts were investigated by means of XPS techniques. Figure 6 (a)
280 displays the deconvoluted photoemission peaks for Ni $2p_{3/2}$ region. For all the analysed
281 samples the main XPS peak located in the range $855\text{-}856\text{ eV}$ and the shake-up satellite
282 peak in the range $861\text{-}862\text{ eV}$ showed that the Ni^{2+} ions were mainly incorporated in the
283 network of NiAl_2O_4 structure [5,23,32]. However, as reported in Table 3, the XPS peak
284 positions seemed to depend on the MgO content. For example, the MgO(5)-NiAl
285 catalyst showed the lowest Ni $2p_{3/2}$ peak binding energy (855.2 eV). This shift was
286 explained by an enrichment of the near surface of MgO(5)-NiAl sample with NiO [5,
287 23]. Moreover, as revealed by the FWHM data reported in Table 3, the MgO(5)-NiAl
288 sample showed the broadest Ni $2p_{3/2}$ peak (3.7 eV), thus suggesting a larger
289 heterogeneity in nickel environments. These observations were in good agreement with

290 the previously described H₂-TPR results which revealed that this sample exhibited,
291 besides the NiAl₂O₄ phase, the highest amount of α -type NiO species. Furthermore, a
292 parallel series of Mg 2p spectra was recorded for the MgO(x)-NiAl samples
293 (Figure 6 (b)). The value of O 1s level was taken as internal reference [33]. As seen in
294 Table 3 the Mg 2p main peak energy shifted from 50.1-50.2 eV for the MgO(x \leq 5)-
295 NiAl catalysts towards lower values for MgO-rich catalysts, MgO(7)-NiAl and
296 MgO(10)-NiAl (49.5 eV and 49.7 eV, respectively). In accordance with He et al. [34],
297 this trend was consistent with an increase of the Mg species film thickness from
298 submonolayer to multilayer coverage. Moreover, the comparison of the Mg 2p peak
299 energy for the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts with those corresponding to pure MgO and
300 MgAl₂O₄ (Table 3) evidenced the increase of MgAl₂O₄ phase contribution with MgO
301 loading which was in good agreement with the H₂-TPR data. Besides the main Mg 2p
302 peak the MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl spectra revealed the appearance of another
303 peak at a binding energy about 5 eV larger than the main peak. In several studies this
304 additional peak was associated with a growth of tridimensional Mg species which
305 formed islands with a critical size [35].

306 Table 3 also includes an estimation of Ni/Al and Mg/Al atomic ratios determined by
307 XPS for each catalyst and their comparison with those determined by WDXRF. It was
308 deduced that the Ni/Al XPS ratio remained almost constant for all the samples
309 (0.22-0.25), but it was lower by 50% with respect to that determined for the bulk
310 analysis (WDXRF). However, the comparison of the Mg/Al bulk ratios (0.06-0.25) with
311 the Mg/Al XPS ratios indicated an apparent enrichment of the near surface with Mg
312 species (0.07 for MgO(2.5)-NiAl, 0.1 for MgO(5)-NiAl, 0.24 for MgO(7)-NiAl and 0.4
313 for MgO(10)-NiAl).

314

Figure 6/Table 3

315 *3.1.5. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)*

316 The reduced MgO(x)-NiAl samples were investigated by transmission electron
317 microscopy (TEM). Figure 7 shows the MgO(x)-NiAl micrographs and the
318 corresponding size distribution histograms. The average Ni particle size was estimated
319 from an accumulated frequency including up to 95% of the total population. Table 2
320 also lists the values of the Ni dispersion and the metallic surface area (S_{Ni}) taking into
321 account the degree of reduction for each catalyst.

322 Examination of all the micrographs revealed the presence of Ni particles with a quasi
323 spherical shape. Nevertheless, the size distribution seemed to be affected by the MgO
324 addition. For the bare nickel aluminate, MgO(0)-NiAl, the distribution diagram
325 consisted of a broad asymmetric peak, including sizes ranged between 5 and 30 nm,
326 with an average size of 13 nm corresponding to a Ni dispersion of 7% (Table 2). By
327 contrast, a narrower and more symmetric distribution was observed in the case of the
328 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts thereby indicating an apparent homogeneity of the Ni particle
329 sizes. Furthermore, in agreement with XRD data, smaller Ni particle sizes were
330 deposited in all the MgO-containing samples (11-11.5 nm, $D = 8.7-9.4\%$), thereby
331 suggesting that the addition of magnesia inhibited the sintering of the metallic phase [7,
332 36-38]. Regarding the metallic surface area, it was observed that slightly higher values
333 were obtained for the MgO modified catalysts $14-15 \text{ m}^2_{Ni} \text{ g}^{-1}$ compared to the
334 Mg(0)-NiAl catalyst ($12 \text{ m}^2_{Ni} \text{ g}^{-1}$) (Table 2).

335 Figure 7

336 *3.1.6. Temperature programmed desorption of CO₂ (CO₂-TPD)*

337 The surface basicity of the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts was characterized by means
338 of CO₂-TPD techniques. Figure 8 (a) shows the corresponding desorption profiles
339 recorded on the samples after pre-adsorption of CO₂ at 40 °C for 1 h. The amounts of

340 desorbed CO₂ extracted from the integration of the bands centred at three temperature
341 ranges (40-150 °C, 150-350 °C and >350 °C) are reported in Table 4. Data
342 corresponding to bare alumina are also included for comparison. Generally, at low
343 temperatures the CO₂ desorption peaks are associated with the decomposition of
344 bicarbonates species adsorbed on the weak basic sites [39]. The second temperature
345 range corresponds to a decomposition of bidentate carbonates species which
346 characterise the medium-strength basic sites, while the desorption peaks at high
347 temperatures (> 350 °C) are assigned to the decomposition of unidentate carbonates
348 species formed on the strong basic sites.

349 It was found that the deposition of reduced Ni species onto the alumina surface
350 dramatically increased the total amount as well as the thermal stability of the adsorbed
351 CO₂ (Figure 8 (a) and Table 4). Indeed, the surface density of CO₂ desorbed from
352 alumina, 0.5 μmol m⁻², was much smaller than that determined for MgO(0)-NiAl,
353 2.7 μmol m⁻². However, the total amount of desorbed CO₂ notably decreased in the
354 magnesia doped catalysts. For example, it was about 1.5 μmol m⁻² for MgO(2.5)-NiAl,
355 1.9 μmol m⁻² for MgO(5)-NiAl and 1.2 μmol m⁻² for MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl.
356 This drop in the basic sites density with the MgO content might be related to the
357 structural evolution of Mg species lying on the surface. Indeed, our characterization
358 results pointed out a progressive enrichment of the catalysts with MgAl₂O₄ species with
359 MgO loading. In this sense, Cosimo et al. [39] found that in samples with Mg/Al < 1
360 segregation of bulk MgAl₂O₄ spinel occurred and caused a loss in the basic site density.
361 Table 4 also gives the distribution of the three types of surface basic sites classified
362 according to their strength. When compared to reduced nickel aluminate the distribution
363 appeared to be influenced by the deposition of MgO. It should be highlighted that,
364 among all the analysed samples, this effect was very strong on the MgO(5)-NiAl sample

365 which presented the lowest density of strong basic sites ($0.5 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$) and the highest
366 density of weak basic sites ($1 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$).

367 To facilitate their comparison the percentage of contribution of each group of basic sites
368 are displayed in Figure 8 (b). For the MgO(0)-NiAl sample the contribution of the
369 weak, medium and strong basic sites was 28.5%, 38.7% and 32.7%, respectively. By
370 contrast, the distribution on the MgO(2.5)-NiAl catalyst evidenced an increase in the
371 fraction of strong basic sites, which accounted for 73.2% of the total amount at the
372 expense of the medium-strength basic sites (5.3%). It was also observed a similar
373 distribution on the MgO-rich samples, MgO(7)-NiAl and MgO(10)-NiAl, thus
374 indicating that the nature of the active sites involved in the adsorption of CO₂ was
375 essentially the same on these two samples. The MgO(5)-NiAl sample presented a
376 distinct behaviour with a major contribution of weak basic sites which represented
377 52.8% of the total basic sites. This apparent weakening of the surface basic sites could
378 be related to the presence of large amounts of highly dispersed Mg species on the
379 surface.

380 Due to their relatively higher stability compared to weak basic sites a special attention
381 was paid to the relationship between the amounts of medium and strong basic sites
382 amounts and MgO loading. Figure 8 (c) displays the dependence of the density of basic
383 sites with this strength on the Mg/Al ratios determined by XPS (Table 3). The results
384 showed a significant loss in the surface basicity, respect to MgO(0)-NiAl sample
385 ($1.9 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$), with the abundance of Mg on the near surface up to a value of Mg/Al
386 corresponding to 0.1. For higher Mg/Al ratios the density of medium-strong basic sites
387 remained almost constant, about $0.85\text{-}0.9 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$. Then, the number of the sites
388 involved in the medium-strong basicity was essentially the same on all the over-
389 monolayer samples.

3.2. Catalytic performance in the POM reaction

In our previous study on the activity of Ni catalysts in the partial oxidation of methane an indirect two-step mechanism based on total combustion at lower temperatures followed by methane reforming by CO₂ and/or steam at high temperatures was verified. Accordingly we found that at lower temperatures (<650 °C) very low CO/CO₂ ratios were obtained thereby suggesting a high combustion activity and a low reforming activity [23]. This poor reforming activity at low temperatures induced, moreover, was related to drastic changes in the Ni oxidation state since inactive NiO was preferentially formed. For this reason, the catalytic tests were carried out at high temperature (700 °C).

3.2.1. Stoichiometric operating conditions ($O/C = 1$)

Figure 9 (left) shows the evolution of methane conversion and H₂ yield with time on stream at 700 °C and 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ over the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts. The activity data of a commercial RhAl catalyst was also included for the sake of comparison. As a general behaviour, all the samples exhibited a marked stability in the studied time on stream. Over the MgO-free nickel aluminate sample, MgO(0)-NiAl, both high activity (75%) and H₂ yield (0.84) were found (Table 5). The addition of 2.5% of MgO seemed to provoke a significant decrease in its activity (71%) and the yields of H₂ (0.76) and CO (0.62). However, the addition of MgO concentrations higher than 2.5% induced an improvement of the catalytic performance. For instance, the MgO(5)-NiAl catalyst proved the highest methane conversion (83%), close to that attained by the rhodium catalyst and the thermodynamic equilibrium value (86%), and the highest yields of H₂ and CO (0.92 and 0.75, respectively) whereas it exhibited the lowest yield of CO₂ (0.08). According to their catalytic activity and H₂ yield the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts followed this trend: MgO(5)-NiAl > MgO(7)-NiAl >

415 MgO(10)-NiAl > MgO(0)-NiAl > MgO(2.5)-NiAl. On another hand, it should be noted
416 that the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts demonstrated a relatively good resistance against the
417 coke formation which was lower than 7.3% (Table 5).

418 Figure 9/Table 5

419 The spent catalysts were analysed by XRD in order to determine the nature of deposited
420 carbon and to evaluate the Ni particle sizes. The patterns of the post-run samples
421 (not displayed) showed the appearance of graphitic carbon phase with low intensity
422 signals. On the other hand, the Ni particle sizes estimated by means of Scherrer equation
423 showed generally slight changes (Table 2). Among all the used catalysts the
424 MgO(2.5)-NiAl catalyst presented the largest particle growth (from 9.5 nm to 13 nm).
425 Table 5 also lists the measured H₂/CO and CO/CO₂ ratios. The H₂/CO ratios over the
426 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts were in all the cases around 2.7-2.9. These relatively high
427 values (> 2) could explain the high stability of the catalysts due to the
428 non-encapsulation of the metal particles by deposited carbon [40]. In our previous study
429 on the performance of the Ni/alumina in the partial oxidation of methane we reported
430 that an increase in active metal dispersion led to higher H₂/CO ratios and an enhanced
431 stability of the catalysts [23]. Accordingly, the similar dispersion of Ni particles, in the
432 7-9% range, on the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts could explain the similar obtained H₂/CO
433 ratio values. However, the analysis of the CO/CO₂ ratio values, ranged between 6.2 and
434 9.6, revealed significant differences among the samples. Generally, the production of
435 CO₂ is related to the occurrence of CO disproportionation and/or methane total
436 oxidation reactions [23]. The gasification of deposited carbon by the produced water (as
437 a product of CH₄ combustion) is one of the reasons that might explain the low carbon
438 deposition detected on the used catalysts.

439 Since no marked differences were observed in the dispersion of metallic nickel among
440 all the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts a special attention was devoted to an examination of the
441 influence of structural and chemical properties induced by the Mg species on their
442 catalytic properties. Figure 10 shows the influence of the strong basic sites density
443 measured by CO₂-TPD on the activity (X(CH₄)) and the product distribution (Y(H₂) and
444 CO/CO₂ ratio). The results showed a clear correlation between the surface chemical
445 properties and the catalytic properties of the samples since revealed a decrease in
446 methane conversion and H₂ yields with increasing density of strong basic sites.
447 Furthermore, the dependence trace of CO/CO₂ ratio on the strong basic sites density
448 showed that the reforming activity was governed by the density of strong basic sites.
449 Hence, the sample presenting the lowest strong basic sites density,
450 MgO(5)-NiAl, exhibited the highest reforming activity.

451 According to Cosimo et al. [39] the strong basic sites that presented high stability
452 predominantly consisted of O²⁻ anions. Moreover, in their study on the mechanism of
453 the POM over a Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst Jin et al. [41] established that the surface intermediate
454 Ni-C species could react with two types of oxygen species. The first oxygen species
455 named mobile was a product of the activation of oxygen which could react with Ni-C
456 species to produce CO whereas the second species consisted of chemisorbed O²⁻ species
457 which reacted with Ni-C species to produce CO₂. These data could explain the
458 difference observed in the catalytic behaviour of our investigated materials. The
459 observed decrease in the CO/CO₂ ratio with the increase of strong basic density could
460 be associated with the increased amounts of O²⁻ ions which could enhance the formation
461 of CO₂ at the expense of the CO formation.

462 Figure 10

463 3.2.2. *Non-stoichiometric operating conditions (O/C = 0.75)*

464 In order to examine the stability of the prepared MgO(x)-NiAl samples catalytic runs
465 under more severe conditions were conducted with a higher volume hourly space
466 velocity, namely $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$, and a lower O/C molar ratio (from 1 to 0.75)
467 (Figure 9 (right)). As expected, the selected conditions provoked a decrease in the initial
468 activity of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts and an apparent deactivation with time on stream.
469 The amount of deposited carbon was larger than 24 wt.% for all the used catalysts
470 suggesting that the observed deactivation was essentially associated with poisoning of
471 active sites by coke precursors. For instance, the initial methane conversion over the
472 MgO(5)-NiAl catalyst was around 65% (versus 83% obtained with O/C = 1). Even so it
473 kept its superior behaviour compared to the rest of the catalysts. In line with the
474 catalytic results under softer conditions, the initial methane conversion over the studied
475 catalysts seemed to have a similar correlation with the density of strong basic sites
476 densities discussed above. Indeed, it decreased from 65% for the catalyst with the
477 lowest strong sites density, MgO(5)-NiAl, to 54% over the catalyst with the highest
478 strong sites density, MgO(2.5)-NiAl. It should be highlighted that, under non-
479 stoichiometric operating conditions (O/C = 0.75), the MgO addition seemed to improve
480 the resistance against sintering (Table 2). For instance, the Ni particle size on the
481 MgO(0)-NiAl catalyst increased from 9 to 17.5 nm while it did not reach 15 nm on all
482 the Mg catalysts.

483 Figure 11 shows the dependence of the activity loss (%), evaluated as the difference
484 between initial conversion and conversion at 20 h divided by the initial conversion, on
485 the MgO loading. For the bare sample, MgO(0)-NiAl, the activity decreased by 5%. The
486 loss of activity upon increasing the MgO content seemed to depend on the differences in
487 the textural properties among the tested catalysts. The addition of an amount of MgO

488 lower than the theoretical monolayer dispersion value improved the stability of the
489 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts. By contrast, the catalysts with an over-monolayer MgO
490 amounts exhibited a poorer stability when compared to the MgO-free sample. In
491 accordance with our characterisation results it could be concluded that the highly
492 dispersed Mg species enhanced the stability of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts whereas an
493 enrichment of the surface with the over-monolayer Mg species accelerated the
494 deactivation of the catalysts.

495 Figure 11

496 Given the promising behaviour of MgO(5)-NiAl its performance was evaluated for a
497 considerably more prolonged reaction time interval (75 h) (Figure 12). For comparison
498 the MgO(7)-NiAl catalyst was also investigated. The results showed that despite the
499 comparable amounts of deposited carbon (64-68 wt.%) and Ni particle sizes (20-21 nm)
500 the MgO(5)-NiAl catalyst maintained its superiority in terms of catalytic performance
501 and stability with respect to the MgO(7)-NiAl catalyst (Table 5). This comparison
502 meant that the catalytic performance differences in the POM reaction were not a
503 function of the active nickel state (dispersion and the corresponding deposited carbon
504 amounts). This might point out, however, that the improved structural and chemical
505 properties provided by the highly dispersed Mg species played a key role in the
506 enhancement of the activity and the stability of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts in the POM
507 reaction.

508 Figure 12

509

510 4. Conclusions

511 Bulk nickel aluminate spinel (NiAl_2O_4) was synthesised by precipitation and
512 subsequently loaded with varying amounts of MgO (2.5-10 wt.%). The samples in both

513 calcined and reduced catalysts were thoroughly characterised by a wide number of
514 analytical techniques including BET, XRD, H₂-TPR, XPS, TEM and CO₂-TPD. By
515 combining the information obtained from all these studies, a detailed description of the
516 texture, structure, Mg and Ni distribution and chemical properties of the catalysts could
517 be proposed.

518 The addition of magnesia to the nickel aluminate spinel induced the formation of nickel
519 species with different chemical nature, namely NiO-MgO solid solution, mixed
520 (Ni,Mg)Al₂O₄ spinel and relatively hardly reducible NiO and NiAl₂O₄ phases. In
521 contrast to the calcined samples, the formation of MgAl₂O₄ was much more pronounced
522 on the reduced samples because of the presence of large amounts of the alumina as a
523 consequence of the reduction of nickel aluminate, which subsequently interact with
524 MgO to form MgAl₂O₄ phase. Moreover, on the MgO doped catalysts the metallic
525 nickel particles exhibited a slightly higher resistance to sintering compared to those
526 derived from the bare NiAl₂O₄ spinel. In addition, the presence of magnesium species
527 also provoked drastic changes in the number of surface basic sites and their distribution,
528 which could be modulated by modifying the MgO content.

529 The catalytic behaviour of the reduced samples was investigated in the partial oxidation
530 of methane. The results showed that the modification of NiAl₂O₄ by MgO with a
531 concentration higher than 2.5 wt.% clearly enhanced its catalytic performance which
532 was close to that of a commercial Rh catalyst. It was also found that the reforming
533 efficiency (conversion, H₂ yield and stability) could be tuned by controlling the surface
534 strong basic sites density. The MgO(5)-NiAl sample with a magnesium loading close to
535 the theoretical monolayer exhibited the lower density of strong basic sites and the best
536 catalytic performance.

537

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- 619

620 **CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES**

621 Table 1. Elemental analysis and textural properties of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

622 Table 2 Reducibility and structural properties of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

623 Table 3 XPS study of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

624 Table 4 Surface basic sites properties as determined by CO₂-TPD study.

625 Table 5 Catalytic performance of the MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts in the POM reaction.

626

627 Figure 1 Pore sizes distribution for the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

628 Figure 2 XRD patterns of the (a) calcined and (b) reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

629 Figure 3 Correlation between the lattice parameter corresponding to γ -alumina and
630 the Mg/Al molar ratios as determined by WDXRF.

631 Figure 4 H₂-TPR profiles of the calcined MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

632 Figure 5 Dependence of the reduction peak temperatures on the MgO loading for the
633 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

634 Figure 6 XPS spectra for the (a) Ni 2p_{3/2} and (b) Mg 2p regions of the calcined
635 MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts.

636 Figure 7 TEM images and Ni particle sizes distribution of the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl
637 catalysts.

638 Figure 8 (a) CO₂-TPD profiles of the reduced MgO(x)-NiAl catalysts, (b) the
639 contribution of each basic sites strength group and (c) the dependence of the
640 density of the medium-strong surface basic sites on the Mg/Al XPS ratios.

641 Figure 9 Catalytic performance in terms of CH₄ conversion and hydrogen yield as a
642 function of time. Reaction conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹;
643 10%CH₄/5%O₂/85%N₂; W = 0.125 g; 700 °C; 20 h (left) and

644 $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; 15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂; W = 0.125 g; 700 °C;
645 20 h (right).

646 Figure 10 The influence of the strong basic sites density measured by CO₂-TPD on the
647 activity (X(CH₄),%) and the product distribution (Y(H₂) and CO/CO₂ ratio).
648 Reaction conditions: $38400 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; 10%CH₄/5%O₂/85%N₂;
649 W = 0.125 g; 700 °C; 20 h.

650 Figure 11 Dependence of the activity loss (%) in non-stoichiometric conditions
651 (O/C = 0.75) on the MgO loadings.

652 Figure 12 Stability performance in terms of CH₄ conversion and hydrogen yield over
653 MgO(5)-NiAl and MgO(7)-NiAl catalysts as a function of time. Reaction
654 conditions: $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; 15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂;
655 W = 0.125 g; 700 °C; 75 h.

656

657

658

Catalysts	Ni, wt.% ^(a)	MgO, wt.% ^(a)	S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	W _p , nm	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹
MgO(0)-NiAl	(32.1)	(0)	67 (75)	14.4 (12.7)	0.32 (0.30)
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	(31.5)	(2.4)	64 (68)	14.5 (12.9)	0.29 (0.29)
MgO(5)-NiAl	(31)	(4.9)	62 (62)	15 (13.8)	0.29 (0.28)
MgO(7)-NiAl	(30.4)	(7)	59 (61)	15.5 (13.9)	0.28 (0.28)
MgO(10)-NiAl	(29.7)	(10)	59 (59)	16.6 (15.4)	0.31 (0.28)

Values in brackets correspond to the calcined catalysts.

^(a)Determined by WDXRF

659

660

Table 1

Catalysts	H ₂ -TPR					TEM				XRD (Ni ⁰ particle size, nm)		
	H ₂ uptake, mmol g ⁻¹	Relative amount of NiO species, % ^(a)				Reduction degree, %	Ni ⁰ particle size, nm	D, % ^(b)	S _{Ni} ^(c) , m ² _{Ni} g ⁻¹	Reduced catalysts	Spent catalysts ^(d)	Spent catalysts ^(e)
		α	β	γ	θ							
MgO(0)-NiAl	5.6	19 (490)	39 (720)	42 (805)	0	100	13	7.0	12	11	9.	18
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	5.6	22 (480)	40 (740)	38 (815)	0	100	11	8.9	15	9.5	13	14
MgO(5)-NiAl	5.1	25 (525)	40 (750)	35 (825)	0	100	11.5	8.7	15	9	12	13.5
MgO(7)-NiAl	5.2	12 (480)	59 (720)	25 (835)	4 (>860)	100	11	9.4	15	9	11	15
MgO(10)-NiAl	4.7	16 (505)	49 (715)	26 (860)	10 (>860)	94	11	8.7	14	9	9	13

^(a)Values in brackets correspond to the peak temperature (°C) of each reduction band.

^(b)Ni dispersion taking into account the extent of reduction at 850 °C.

^(c)Metallic surface area taking into account the extent of reduction at 850 °C.

^(d)Reaction conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 10%CH₄/5%O₂/85%N₂; 700 °C; 20 h.

^(e)Reaction conditions: 60000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂; 700 °C; 20 h.

661

662

Table 2

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Catalysts	Main Ni 2p _{3/2} , eV	FWHM main Ni 2p _{3/2} , eV	Main Mg 2p, eV	Main O 1s, eV	Ni/Al	Mg/Al	Ni/Al ^(a)	Mg/Al ^(a)
MgO(0)-NiAl	855.7	3.5	-	530.6	0.22	0.00	0.50	0.00
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	855.6	3.0	50.1	530.6	0.24	0.07	0.51	0.06
MgO(5)-NiAl	855.2	3.7	50.2	530.3	0.25	0.10	0.50	0.11
MgO(7)-NiAl	855.4	3.4	49.5	530.4	0.22	0.24	0.51	0.17
MgO(10)-NiAl	855.6	3.4	49.7	530.0	0.25	0.40	0.51	0.25
MgO	-	-	50.4	-	-	-	-	-
MgAl ₂ O ₄	-	-	49.4	-	-	-	-	-

^(a)Determined by WDXRF.

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Table 3

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Catalysts	Total surface basic sites density, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$	Weak basic sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$	Medium-strength basic sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$	Strong basic sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$
$\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$	0.5	0.16	0.21	0.13
MgO(0)-NiAl	2.7	0.77	1.04	0.88
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	1.5	0.32	0.08	1.10
MgO(5)-NiAl	1.9	1.00	0.40	0.50
MgO(7)-NiAl	1.2	0.33	0.24	0.64
MgO(10)-NiAl	1.2	0.38	0.18	0.64

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Table 4

Catalysts	X(CH ₄), %	Y(H ₂)	Y(CO)	Y(CO ₂)	H ₂ /CO	CO/CO ₂	Coke, wt. %
Equilibrium	86	0.92	0.81	0.06	2.3	14.6	-
MgO(0)-NiAl	75	0.84	0.65	0.1	2.8	6.2	2.8
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	71	0.76	0.62	0.09	2.7	6.6	7.3
MgO(5)-NiAl	83	0.92	0.75	0.08	2.8	9.6	5.7
MgO(7)-NiAl	78	0.90	0.68	0.1	2.9	7.2	0.7
MgO(10)-NiAl	77	0.87	0.68	0.09	2.8	7.5	6.5
RhAl	86	0.66	0.77	0.09	1.7	8.8	1.7

Reaction conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 10%CH₄/5%O₂/85%N₂; W = 0.125 g; 700 °C; 20 h

Catalysts	X(CH ₄), %	Y(H ₂)	Y(CO)	Y(CO ₂)	H ₂ /CO	CO/CO ₂	Coke, wt. %
Equilibrium	62	0.90	0.58	0.04	3.1	13.7	-
MgO(0)-NiAl	57	0.41	0.49	0.08	1.7	6.3	43
MgO(2.5)-NiAl	54	0.37	0.44	0.10	1.7	4.6	24
MgO(5)-NiAl	63	0.46	0.56	0.07	1.7	7.8	47
MgO(7)-NiAl	59	0.43	0.51	0.08	1.7	6.7	31
MgO(10)-NiAl	53	0.39	0.43	0.10	1.8	4.3	40
RhAl	61	0.45	0.55	0.07	1.6	8.1	2

Reaction conditions: 60000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 15.6%CH₄/5.9%O₂/78.5%N₂; W=0.125 g; 700 °C; 20 h/75 h

MgO(5)-NiAl (75 h)	60	0.45	0.53	0.07	1.7	7.5	68
MgO(7)-NiAl (75 h)	56	0.42	0.47	0.09	1.8	5.4	64

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Table 5

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

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Figure 5

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Figure 6

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Figure 7

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Figure 8

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Figure 9

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Figure 10

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Figure 11

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Figure 12